

CHANNEL SWITCHING IN FASHION: UNVEILING THE ROLES OF PERCEIVED THREAT, SELF-EFFICACY, AND ATTITUDE

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Abstract

In an era marked by rapid innovations in marketing and shifting consumer preferences, this study explores the intricate dynamics of channel switching intentions within the realm of fashion consumption, contextualized by the most recent marketing trends and consumers' evolving shopping behaviors. Grounded in the Theory of Planned Behavior and Protection Motivation Theory, this study scrutinizes the impacts of perceived severity, perceived vulnerability, self-efficacy, and response efficiency as independent variables, with attitude serving as a mediator and channel switching intention as the dependent variable. Data was collected from a sample of fashion consumers to analyze the relationships between under study variables and the attitude towards channel switching intention. The sample size is determined using a power analysis technique to ensure sufficient statistical power. Data analysis is involving structural equation modelling (SEM) to test the proposed hypotheses. The variables of the study are measured using a Likert scale adapted from previous research studies. The findings indicate that consumers' attitudes towards different shopping channels are significantly influenced by their perceptions of severity and vulnerability. Additionally, the efficiency of their response and their belief in their own capability (self-efficacy) to use a particular channel also play a role in shaping their attitudes and subsequent intentions to switch channels. This study contributes to the existing literature on channel switching behavior in the fashion industry. The insights gained from this research can be valuable for retailers in developing strategies to retain customers and reduce channel switching. The value of this research lies in its contribution to channel-switching research by filling the gap of traditionally ignored dimensions of threat appraisal, coping responses, and consumer attitude. Through the analysis of these variables, the research seeks to provide a more profound insight into fashion consumers' switching attitudes and generate useful implications for retailers and marketers in designing sound customer retention strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Consumer behavior is a field of study that is in a constant state of evolution; this is especially true for the fashion industry, which has been drastically impacted by the emergence of social media and technology (Sarwar et al., 2024). Fashion can be explained as when applied on wearable clothing, “a style of dress that is temporarily adopted by a noticeable proportion of members of a social group because that chosen style is perceived to be appropriate for the time and situation” (Taylor & Costello, 2017). Fashion is regarded as one of the most important global industries and because of its evolutionary nature; new tendencies and trends constantly appear (Casaló, Flavián, & Ibáñez-Sánchez, 2020). Due to technological advancements, evolving market dynamics, and the influence of global events, fashion consumers are consistently re-evaluating their shopping habits. South Asian countries like Pakistan, Bangladesh, and India are now becoming a hub for apparel manufacturing, and approximately 60% of the total garments now being consumed by the individuals around the world are prepared in these three countries (Razzaq, Ansari, Razzaq, & Awan, 2018).

Customer is king, and consumer behavior is considered an exciting topic for marketing and academic researchers (Reardon et al., 2022). Consumer behavior can be hard to predict, but luckily, there are several approaches, such as the analytical, cognitive, and economic approach, that can help us understand how consumers behave in different contexts (Liang et al., 2018). In recent years, due to drastic changes in technology, consumer behaviors are even more complicated (Saibu et al., 2023).

The retail industry is changing because the modern consumer is different from before. They are more conscious about brands and quality and have enough knowledge and information related to the product (Collison et al., 2021). They have more money, have more time, and are more interested in different shopping experiences than ever. Retailers are learning that shoppers are using multiple channels to buy the product, and they are shopping more often across several sales channels (Xu et al., 2021). Therefore, the study shows that the behavior called consumer channel migration. One aspect of consumer behavior

that is of particular interest to fashion marketers is the phenomenon of switching intentions (Nasir et al., 2022). In the context of fashion, switching intentions may arise when a consumer becomes dissatisfied with a particular brand or product or when they are attracted to a new brand or product that better aligns with their needs or preferences (Putri et al., 2022). Understanding switching intentions is essential for fashion marketers, as it can help them develop effective strategies for retaining existing customers and attracting new ones.

Several factors can influence switching intentions in fashion (Jain et al., 2023). Consumers are more likely to switch to a new brand or product if they believe that it is of higher quality than their current brand or product. Another important factor is the perceived value of money (Sarwar et al., 2025; 2024). Perceived severity can have a direct impact on attitude formation. For instance, if consumers perceive a product quality issue as severe, they are more likely to develop negative attitudes toward the brand or the company responsible for the problem. The severity of the issue amplifies the negative evaluation, leading to a more unfavorable attitude (Zainab et al., 2024). When consumers perceive a problem to be severe, they are motivated to seek information, evaluate alternatives, and engage in a more thorough cognitive appraisal (Li et al., 2020). This increased cognitive effort can shape attitudes as consumers gather more information and consider the severity of the issue in their evaluation. On the other hand, attitudes can also influence perceived severity. An individual's pre-existing attitudes towards a brand, product, or service can affect their perception of severity. For example, consumers with a positive attitude towards a brand may be more likely to downplay the severity of a negative experience or rationalize the problem. Conversely, consumers with negative attitudes may amplify the perceived severity, reinforcing their negative evaluation (Sarwar et al., 2020).

Perceived vulnerability refers to the extent to which fashion consumers perceive risks, uncertainties, or adverse outcomes associated with channel switching (Birkmeyer et al., 2021). It encompasses concerns about factors such as product quality, confidentiality and security issues, delivery reliability, and the overall unfamiliarity with the new channel. The

attitude of fashion consumers towards channel switching represents their overall evaluation or favorability towards engaging in this behavior (Ferreira et al., 2022; Nasir et al., 2022). When fashion consumers perceive a high level of vulnerability associated with channel switching, it often leads to a negative attitude toward engaging in these behaviors (Sarwar et al., 2024; Sarwar et al., 2023). So, the relationship between perceived vulnerability and the attitude of fashion consumers with channel switching intention can range from negative to positive, with the potential for moderation based on the level of perceived vulnerability (Rajab et al., 2019). Understanding this relationship can help fashion marketers and retailers develop strategies to address consumers' concerns, emphasize the benefits of channel switching, and encourage a positive attitude towards these behaviors.

The rapid growth of technology and digital platforms has revolutionized the way fashion consumers interact with retailers and brands. Consumers now have the freedom to choose from a variety of channels, including in-store, online platforms, social media, and customer service helplines, to engage with fashion companies. This plethora of options has led to an increased likelihood of channel switching among consumers (Arora et al., 2018). Channel-switching intentions can have significant implications for fashion companies, as they can result in reduced customer loyalty and satisfaction (Laato et al., 2020). Hence, understanding the association within response efficiency, attitude, and channel-switching intentions is essential for businesses to effectively manage customer interactions across channels. According to certain recent studies Channel switching, the behavior where consumers shift their purchasing preferences between online and offline channels, has gained significant traction in the modern fashion market (Kashif et al., 2021; Vigolo and Ugolini, 2016). While prior studies have considered various factors that influence this behavior (Abbas et al., 2021; Ahmed et al., 2019; Vehmas et al., 2018). However, less is understood about the psychological factors and how they play into this behaviour, especially in the realm of fashion apparel consumption (Gul et al., 2021; Fatima et al., 2022).

Despite the increased incidence of channel switching, there is limited understanding of what influences consumer intentions in this regard. A better understanding of these psychological factors and the mediating role of attitude will not only deepen academic insights but will also provide fashion retailers with a clearer understanding of how to retain customers and minimize channel switching (Mahmood et al., 2022). By bridging these gaps, the proposed research seeks to provide a more complete understanding of the complex network of factors influencing channel-switching intentions in the context of Pakistan's fashion apparel retail industry. This holistic perspective offers valuable insights for fashion retailers and marketers seeking to tailor strategies that align with the evolving needs and preferences of consumers while staying current with the latest fashion trends.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The subsequent sections explain the conceptual framework employed to investigate the perceived benefits and risks' role in fashion consumers' channel-switching behavior. Following a description of the theories applied, the research hypotheses are presented and the suggested relations explained through a conceptual model.

2.1 Protection Motivation Theory (PMT)

The Protection Motivation Theory (PMT) is a social cognitive theory that explains how people respond to perceived threats or dangers, particularly in the context of behavior outcomes. According to PMT, two cognitive processes influence people's behavior. Threat appraisal involves an individual's assessment of a threat's potential harm or severity and their evaluation of the likelihood of the hazard occurring (Liu et al., 2023). PMT proposes that the interaction between these two cognitive processes determines an individual's motivation to engage in protective behaviors. Coping appraisal refers to the consumer's perception of their ability to cope with the threat associated with the channel. If consumers perceive the threat as severe and their coping ability as low, they may be motivated to switch channels to avoid the perceived risk (Sarwar et al., 2023). Therefore, fashion retailers can use PMT to understand the factors influencing their customers' channel-

switching intentions and respond appropriately to reduce the perceived risks associated with a particular channel (Liu et al., 2023).

2.2 The Theory of Planned Behavior

The TPB is a theory in social psychology that tries to explain and forecast human behavior. According to TPB, human behavior is influenced by three main factors: attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Attitudes refer to an individual's positive or negative evaluation of a behavior (Bosnjak et al., 2020). The Theory of Planned Behavior offers a structured approach for examining attitudes towards behaviors. The individual's attitude towards a particular behavior encompasses evaluations of its outcomes, subjective norms, normative beliefs, and the motivation to conform. Attitude, perceived behavior, and subjective norms are the three key components of beliefs posited by the theory, which aim to elucidate future behavioral intentions (Nasir et al., 2022). The TPB provides a valuable framework for understanding the inclination of fashion consumers to change channels. This theory considers various individual and social factors that impact their behavior (Arora & Sahney et al., 2018).

2.3 Perceived Severity

Severity is harm or threat that may pose a social, psychological, economic, or other danger to self or other species. When fashion consumers become aware of the perceived severity associated with their current shopping channel, it can trigger thoughts about the potential harm or threats they might face in continuing to use that channel. They might explore alternative shopping channels that they perceive to be less severe in terms of the issues they are trying to avoid (Liu et al., 2023). The fear appeal might include statistics on the percentage of late deliveries or customer testimonials highlighting the frustration caused by such delays. As a result of this message and the heightened perception of severity, fashion consumers may be more inclined to consider channel switching as a solution to mitigate the identified threats or harms (Guo et al., 2021).

They might explore alternative shopping channels that they perceive to be less severe in terms of the issues they are trying to avoid. So, the concept of perceived severity, when influenced by effective fear

appeals and applied to the fashion consumer context, can significantly impact channel switching intentions (Floyd et al., 2000). The experience that part of the social or psychological harm inflicted on oneself or others is a belief about possible damage in the past because one is motivated to protect one or others (Wang et al., 2023).

Another potential threat for fashion consumers when shopping through specific channels is their privacy and security. The fear of identity theft or unauthorized access to their data is a significant worry (Jansen et al., 2018). Studies have shown that perceived inconvenience, additional cost, and risk could reduce consumers' intention to switch channels in the fashion industry (Lin & Wu et al., 2014; Park & Kim., 2019).

According to the protection motivation theory proceeds, variety is an important consideration that influences the attitude of fashion consumers toward channel-switching behavior. When consumers believe that their current shopping channel poses severe threats to their shopping experience, they are more likely to explore alternative channels to mitigate those threats and improve their overall satisfaction and convenience (Teasdale et al., 2022).

H1: Perceived severity positively influence the channel switching intention.

H2: Perceived severity positively influences the attitude of fashion consumers.

2.4 Perceived Vulnerability

Perceived vulnerability in the context of fashion consumers refers to individuals' beliefs regarding their susceptibility to negative outcomes or dissatisfaction with their current shopping channel or the fashion products they are considering (Chang et al., 2022). Perceived vulnerability plays a significant role in shaping attitudes toward various situations, objects, or behaviors (De Coninck et al., 2020). When fashion consumers perceive themselves as vulnerable in their current shopping channel, such as having concerns about product quality, delivery reliability, or customer service, they are likely to develop a negative attitude toward that channel. This negative attitude arises from the perceived risks associated with the channel and the belief that it may not meet their expectations (Wang et al., 2023).

Some researchers propose that perceived risk plays a significant role in a consumer's shopping decision through a particular retail channel. According to this viewpoint, consumers who perceive less risk online than offline are more likely to transition to online channels than consumers who perceive higher levels of risk (Ahorsu et al., 2020). Conversely, if consumers feel that their current channel is relatively reliable and that the fashion items they purchase are of good quality, they may have lower channel switching intentions. Their perceived lack of vulnerability reduces the motivation to explore alternative channels since the current choice is less threatening (Youn et al., 2021).

These findings indicate that the perceived vulnerability has a positive impact on consumers' likelihood to switch channels. Research has shown that perceived vulnerability can be a significant attitude driver while channel switching intention (Homburg et al., 2017; Youn et al., 2021). Furthermore, channel switching can be a way for consumers to reduce their perceived vulnerability by gaining more control over the shopping experience perceived vulnerability directly impacts the attitudes of fashion consumers. When individuals perceive themselves as vulnerable, they are more likely to develop negative attitudes toward their current shopping channel and the fashion items they consider as potential threats. These negative attitudes, in turn, can drive consumers to have stronger channel switching intentions, as they seek to minimize perceived risks and improve their overall shopping experience by exploring alternative channels (Wang et al., 2020).

H3: Perceived vulnerability positively influences the channel switching intention.

H4: Perceived vulnerability positively influences the attitude of fashion consumers.

2.5 Response efficiency

Response efficiency directly affects the perceived efficacy of switching channels. If consumers believe that switching will be straightforward, they are more likely to believe that it will effectively address the issues they face, such as finding better deals or more fashionable items (Kim et al., 2022). Response efficiency can shape a consumer's attitude toward channel switching. If it's easy to switch, consumers

are more likely to have a positive attitude toward this behavior (Krath et al., 2022).

One study by (Yuen et al., 2022) found that people who switch between physical stores and online platforms have a more challenging time making decisions compared to those who only use one channel. Another study by (Liu et al., 2020) found that people who switch from physical stores to online platforms have more difficulties making decisions. They get overwhelmed with too much information and too many choices compared to those who only shop in physical stores (Wang et al., 2022).

However, it is essential to note that the relationship between response efficiency, attitude, and channel-switching intention may also be influenced by other factors, such as the perceived costs associated with switching channels, the perceived quality of the different channels, and the individual's prior experiences with channel switching (Jacquet et al., 2018). When consumers perceive that they can effectively complete the coping reaction to avoid undesirable results, they have an unfavorable evaluation. TPB posits that individuals' attitudes toward a behavior significantly influence their intention to engage in that behavior. In the context of fashion channel-switching, this behavior is switching from one channel to another. Response efficiency aligns with attitude formation because it can shape how consumers perceive this behavior (Xu et al., 2021). If channel-switching is seen as convenient and beneficial (due to response efficiency), consumers are more likely to have a positive attitude toward it (Manss et al., 2020).

H5: Response efficiency negatively influences the channel switching intentions.

H6: Response efficiency negatively influences the attitude of fashion consumers.

2.6 Self-Efficacy

This self-efficacy can be categorized into two main types: Perceived Self-Efficacy relates to consumers' subjective beliefs about their capability to switch channels successfully. Consumers with high actual self-efficacy have a track record of successfully switching between channels when shopping for fashion items. However, switching between channels may also introduce additional cognitive and

behavioral costs that hinder consumers' decision-making efficiency (Putri et al., 2022).

When examining the procedure of channel migration, the concept of self-efficacy pertains to consumers' perceptions regarding their capability to obtain information about products and complete purchases through different channels (Sutinen et al., 2022). For instance, (Kim and Park et al., 2017) found that consumers who frequently switched between physical stores and online platforms had lower decisions. Consumers who switched from physical stores overload and choice overload than those who only shopped in physical stores (Liu et al., 2020).

Consumers with high self-efficacy are more likely to perceive lower cognitive and behavioral costs when switching channels. They believe they can handle the challenges associated with channel switching efficiently. And the consumers with low self-efficacy may perceive higher cognitive and behavioral costs as they lack confidence in their ability to navigate different channels effectively. Differences in self-efficacy across multiple channels can influence the search phase, as consumers with low self-efficacy may lack confidence in their ability to effectively search across different channels (Nel et al., 2020).

Fashion consumers who believe in their ability to switch channels effectively are more likely to have a strong intention to engage in channel switching (Kwarteng et al., 2023). They are confident that they can navigate different channels to maximize their convenience, product availability, and pricing benefits. Conversely, consumers with low self-efficacy may hesitate to switch channels, even if it could potentially benefit them. Their lack of confidence in their channel-switching abilities may lead to a weaker intention to explore different shopping channels (Haridasan et al., 2021). As a result, this can lead to increased inertia, which is the inclination to continue using the same channel even when other options are available, thus influencing them to maintain loyalty to the current channel. Additionally, these consumers perceive alternative media as less attractive (Nel & Boshoff, 2020; Wang et al., 2019). Self-efficacy, whether perceived or actual, has a negatively impact on fashion consumers' attitudes and intentions towards channel switching. Those with higher self-efficacy are more likely to have

positive attitudes and strong intentions to switch channels, while those with lower self-efficacy may have negative attitudes and weaker intentions.

H7: Self-efficiency negatively influences the channel switching intention.

H8: Self-efficiency negatively influences the attitude of fashion consumers.

2.7 Effect of Attitude Towards channel switching Intention

Attitudes, in the context of fashion consumer behavior, are fundamental to understanding channel switching intentions. These attitudes reflect how fashion consumers evaluate different channels for their shopping activities, attitudes play a pivotal role in shaping channel switching intentions among fashion consumer (Liu et al., 2023). Attitudes are indeed the degree to which individuals have favorable or unfavorable evaluations of specific behaviors related to channel switching (Li et al., 2020). Research has shown that attitudes towards channel switching can be influenced by various factors (Wang et al., 2023). Consumers may develop favorable attitudes towards channel switching if they perceive it as a convenient way to access a broader range of fashion products or if it saves time. The development of behavioral intentions, including channel switching intentions, is influenced by attitudes regarding the probability of achieving desired outcomes and the subjective assessment of associated risks and advantages (Liang et al., 2018).

According to the TPB model, previous studies have consistently indicated that consumers' beliefs, encompassing attitudes, behavioral control, and subjective norms, exert significant influence on their behavioral intentions, such as online fashion product purchases and channel switching (Collison et al., 2021). Hence, we hypothesize that when fashion consumers hold favorable beliefs regarding channel switching, they are more inclined to have stronger intentions to embrace a new channel for purchasing fashion items (Madahi et al., 2014).

The researcher anticipated that when fashion consumers have positive thoughts about changing channels, they are more likely to have stronger intentions to begin using the new channel for purchasing fashion items. Additionally, customers have the ability to transition between various

channels, seeking opportunities to optimize their shopping experience and minimize the expenditures of money, time, and effort (Chang et al., 2022). Through the application of deductive reasoning, it can be inferred that a positive attitude is likely to serve as a motivating factor for consumers to engage in channel switching. Consumer preferences and choices are significantly influenced by attitude, which impacts their perception of convenience, trustworthiness, satisfaction, and overall shopping experience across different channels.

H9: Attitude positively influences the channel switching intentions.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section presents a comprehensive overview of the research methodology employed in the study. The research design was cross-sectional, data collected from fashion consumers who purchase through various channels. Additionally, the data indicate that a quantitative method provides more efficient and accurate estimations of the relationships between the investigated variables, although it may overlook specific contextual insights (Trevena et al., 2013). The sampling size is based on 270 individuals currently using fashion products. The study selected specific areas which are a significant concentration of apparel fashion brands, and the target demographic predominantly makes their purchases in these shopping destinations. The use of self-administered questionnaires was chosen since they are very inexpensive and do not contain the impact of the interviewer while respondents are filling them out (Bryman & Bell, 2011). The selected locations in this study represent the target population and allow for a diverse range of individuals from various fields to be included.

3.1 Measures

This research collects data through a self-administrative questionnaire because it is a standardized form of data collection from the respondent. This research uses the already existing available scale for the study. The variables are

measured by using a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly agree to 5 = strongly disagree). The questions are adapted from previous studies to fit the current study's needs. The study's variables and the sources of the things used to measure them as shown according to the thumb rule, $27 \times 10 = 270$ (Hair et al., 2013). The study variables; Perceived Severity was measured by 4 items (Johnston et al., 2010) and (Sun et al., 2013), Perceived Vulnerability was measured by 5 items (Sun et al., 2013) & (Kwarteng et al., 2023), Response Efficiency was measured by 4 items (Lee et al., 2009), Self-Efficiency was measured by 5 items (Ellen et al., 1991) (Lee et al., 2009), Attitude was measured by 5 items (Kim et al., 2009) and Channel-Switching Intention was measured by 4 items (Ouellette et al., 1998).

4 DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Data analysis plays a crucial role in conducting a study, as it involves subjecting the collected data to various processes in order to test the proposed hypotheses. To ensure reliable and valid results, appropriate data analysis techniques were employed. In the current study, hypothesis testing involves utilizing confirmatory analysis, given that the majority of the variables have been empirically investigated by multiple researchers (Girish et al., 2017). The statistical software SPSS (version 26.) and Structural Equation Modeling was employed in this research to analyze data.

In order to evaluate the dependability and accuracy of the items in the questionnaire, various measures are employed, including Cronbach's alpha, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), composite reliability, and average variance extracted values (Fornell & Cha, 1994). SEM used to analyze the reliability and convergent validity of the reflective constructs in confirmatory factor analysis. To assess construct validity, it is preferable for the standardized estimated loading to be greater than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2013). The accepted thresholds for AVE are 0.50, while both CR and Cronbach's alpha are commonly acceptable at 0.70 (Bagozzi & Dholakia., 2002; Hair et al., 2013).

Table 4.1: Demographic Information1

Variables Name	Categories	Count	Percentages
Gender of the Respondents	Male	102	37.8%
	Female	168	62.2%
Age of the Respondents	18-23	75	27.8%
	24-28	72	26.7%
	29-33	76	28.1%
	34-40	47	17.4%
Occupation	Student	59	21.9%
	Employee	73	27.0%
	Unemployed	82	30.4%
	Both (Student & Employee)	56	20.7%
Qualifications	Intermediate	60	22.2%
	Graduation	100	37.0%
	Masters	94	34.8%
	PhD	16	5.9%
Monthly Income / Pocket Money	Below 50000	44	16.3%
	50001-70000	98	36.3%
	700001-100000	80	29.6%
	Above 100000	48	17.8%

4.1 Correlational Analysis

The Pearson correlation table shows the correlations between the six study variables. A correlation is a quantitative measure that assesses the intensity of the association between two variables. The correlation coefficient, which can range from -1 to 1, provides

valuable insights. A correlation coefficient of -1 indicates a fully negative relationship, a correlation coefficient of 0 signifies no relationship, and a correlation coefficient of 1 indicates a fully positive relationship (Sarwar et al., 2020).

Table 4.2: Pearson’s Correlations Matrix2

	Perceived Severity	Perceived Vulnerability	Response Efficiency	Self-Efficiency	Attitude	Channel Switching Intention
Perceived Severity	1					
Perceived Vulnerability	.692**	1				
Response Efficiency	.512**	.666**	1			
Self-Efficiency	.407**	.478**	.632**	1		
Attitude	.458**	.408**	.358**	.580**	1	
Channel Switching Intention	.509**	.454**	.354**	.536**	.674**	1

“**” Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level of significance

4.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

The Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) shows in table includes six factors referred to as attitude, channel switching intention, perceived severity,

perceived vulnerability, response efficiency, and self-efficacy. The factor loadings, composite reliability (CR) and Average variance extracted (AVE) shows that all values are acceptable.

Table 4.3: The CFA Analysis3

Factors	Items	Factor Loading	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Attitude	AT1	0.700	0.789	0.540
	AT2	0.717		
	AT3	0.752		
	AT4	0.786		
	AT5	0.782		
Channel Switching Intention	CSI1	0.791	0.877	0.641
	CSI2	0.772		
	CSI3	0.837		
	CSI4	0.801		
Perceived Severity	PS1	0.810	0.855	0.598
	PS2	0.666		
	PS3	0.870		
	PS4	0.730		
Perceived Vulnerability	PV1	0.725	0.865	0.562
	PV2	0.793		
	PV3	0.709		
	PV4	0.798		
	PV5	0.719		
Response Efficiency	RE1	0.832	0.859	0.698
	RE2	0.884		
	RE3	0.856		
	RE4	0.765		
Self-Efficiency	SE1	0.734	0.868	0.569
	SE2	0.803		
	SE3	0.782		
	SE4	0.725		
	SE5	0.724		

Here is the diagram of Confirmatory factor Analysis and the particular latent construct is considered valid if its fitness indexes achieved the three Model Fit categories namely Absolute Fit, Incremental Fit and

Parsimonious Fit (Sarwar et al., 2023). The fitness indexes and their respective threshold values are shown in figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1

4.3 Results of Hypotheses Testing

The table 4.4 shows the results of the direct effects that were conducted to test the hypotheses about the relationships between the six factors: attitude, channel switching intention, perceived severity, perceived vulnerability, response efficiency, and self-efficiency. The path coefficient (beta) is a measure of the strength of the causal relationship between two variables. The standard error (S.E) is a measure of the uncertainty in the path coefficient. A smaller standard error indicates greater confidence in the path coefficient. The t-value is a statistical test that is used to determine whether the path coefficient is statistically significant. A t-value of 1.96 or greater

indicates that the path coefficient is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. The p-value is a measure of the probability that the path coefficient is due to chance. A p-value of 0.05 or less indicates that the path coefficient is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. The confidence intervals are a range of values that are likely to contain the true path coefficient. A confidence interval of 95% means that there is a 95% probability that the true path coefficient is within the confidence interval. The hypothesis column shows the hypotheses that were tested and the result column shows all the hypotheses are supported except two hypotheses were not supported.

Table 4.4: Path Coefficients/Direct Effect4

	Beta	Std. Error	t-value	95% confidence interval		P values	Hypothesis
				Lower	Upper		
H ₁ : Perceived Severity → Channel Switching Intention	0.329	0.029	11.29	0.270	0.383	0.000	Supported
H ₂ : Perceived Severity → Attitude	0.481	0.044	10.84	0.392	0.563	0.000	Supported
H ₃ : Perceived Vulnerability → Channel Switching Intention	0.301	0.031	9.68	0.236	0.360	0.000	Supported
H ₄ : Perceived Vulnerability → Attitude	0.440	0.042	10.39	0.354	0.521	0.000	Supported
H ₅ : Response Efficiency → Channel Switching Intention	0.030	0.026	1.175	-0.015	0.084	0.241	Not Supported
H ₆ : Response Efficiency → Attitude	0.044	0.037	1.204	-0.024	0.119	0.229	Not Supported

H7: Self Efficiency -> Attitude	0.105	0.045	2.349	0.012	0.189	0.019	Supported
H8: Self Efficiency -> Channel Switching Intention	0.072	0.031	2.292	0.009	0.135	0.022	Supported
H9: Attitude -> Channel Switching Intention	0.683	0.031	22.33	0.623	0.742	0.000	Supported

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The discussion delves into the pertinent knowledge contributions and practical implications of the study's empirical results. The final part explores the obtained results from the previous chapters to address the research questions, objectives, and hypotheses. The research took into account the ever-changing landscape of fashion trends, and the findings indicate that these trends indeed play a significant role in influencing channel-switching intentions (Manss et al., 2022). The latest fashion trends act as a key driver of consumer behavior in this market, aligning with previous research emphasizing the importance of staying attuned to fashion trends in the retail sector (Saibu et al., 2023). As per results all hypotheses were supported except H5 and H6 which state that Response Efficiency has no effect on Channel Switching Intention and attitude. It is because the insignificant contribution of response efficiency can be indicative of the character of fashion consumption, in which threat appraisal is insufficient, and consumers are influenced by other emotional, habitual, or social determinants. This corroborates the argument that, in hedonic or low-risk contexts such as fashion, rational threat-response models would have to be complemented by alternative theories of behavior to make better predictions.

Ultimately, this study contributes to the existing knowledge on consumer behavior and channel choice in fashion. In conclusion, this study provides a comprehensive view of the intricacies of fashion consumer behavior and channel-switching intentions within fashion apparel industry. By addressing this multifaceted research gap, it offers valuable insights for fashion retailers and marketers, empowering them to craft strategies that resonate with the evolving needs and preferences of fashion consumers while staying in tune with the latest fashion trends. Additionally, the study underscores the importance of context-specific research when analyzing fashion consumer behavior and the role of various

influencing variables in channel switching. It underscores the intricate relationships between variables that influence consumers' channel-switching intentions. The findings presented in this study are intended to serve as a starting point for further exploration and innovation in understanding consumer preferences and behaviors within the ever-changing fashion sector.

This study offers actionable insights for fashion industry managers and marketers by considering practical implications. It suggests specific marketing strategies and tactics that fashion companies can implement to retain and attract consumers during times of crisis. Exploring digital marketing, online customer engagement, and personalized shopping experiences aims to strengthen channel loyalty (Liang et al., 2018). Additionally, the proposal of educational initiatives seeks to enhance consumers' understanding of the safety measures and benefits of online and offline shopping channels. These initiatives can help alleviate perceived vulnerabilities and reduce the likelihood of consumers switching channels. Given the importance of technology in channel switching, the research also investigates the latest technological trends in the fashion industry (Birkmeyer et al., 2022). It assesses their impact on consumers' perceptions of channel convenience, ultimately influencing their intention to switch channels. Moreover, the study acknowledges the relevance of consumer channel-switching behavior across various sectors and highlights the potential applicability of its findings and recommendations beyond the fashion industry (Garga et al., 2019). It emphasizes the transferability of the research to other markets or industries that face similar challenges.

This study was limited to only fashion sector. Consumer behaviour might vary from industry to industry. Future research may seek to replicate the findings of this study in other sectors, such as sports, electronics, and tourism. With the rapid pace of technological advancements, consumer behavior is

ever-evolving. Future research might encounter different behaviors that might not align with the current model of perceived severity, vulnerability, response efficiency, self-efficacy, and attitude.

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